

Compulsive Buying an Outcome of the Customers Preference with the Mediating Effect of Brand Attachment

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Abstract

Purpose – This study investigates the role of compulsive buying behavior (CBB) in the mediating effect of brand attachment. Given the negative consequences and increasing prevalence of CBB, it is important to understand how marketing activities influence consumers with varying degrees of CBB tendencies.

Design/methodology/approach – A structured questionnaire was distributed to residents of Islamabad and Rawalpindi using Google Forms. Through convenience and snowball sampling, 361 valid responses were collected and analyzed. The questionnaire was based on literature focusing on branded clothing. Data analysis was performed using SPSS and Smart PLS.

Findings – The results indicate that brand attachment significantly mediates the relationship between materialism, utilitarian value, and compulsive buying. This suggests that brand attachment, especially among young consumers in Pakistan's rapidly growing economy, influences their tendency towards compulsive buying.

Research limitations/implications – This study is limited to residents of Islamabad and Rawalpindi. To generalize findings, future research should include a larger, cross-cultural sample from other Pakistani cities. Additionally, incorporating more variables that influence brand attachment and examining online compulsive buying in the context of increasing e-commerce would provide a more comprehensive understanding.

Practical implications – The findings offer practical insights for marketers. Understanding young consumers' behavior and the role of brand attachment is crucial for developing effective marketing strategies, including product packaging and communication, particularly targeting impulsive buyers of branded apparel.

Originality/value – This study is one of the first to explore the mediating role of brand attachment in compulsive buying behavior among Pakistani consumers, focusing on their preferences for branded clothing.

Keywords Brand attachment, Compulsive buying, Self-congruence, Materialism, Hedonic value, Utilitarian value

1. INTRODUCTION

Consumer behavior experts linked with shopaholic and lavish buying (Xian et al., 2020), frequently refer to compulsive buying (CB) as a sort of behavioral addiction. When people make impulsive purchases to stay up with their friends or to forgo perceived opportunities, it can lead to compulsive buying behaviors (CBB) (Granero et al., 2016; Tarka et al., 2022). As a result, consumers involve in purchase to relieve stress and get away from life's stresses. (Zhengetal., 2020). Compulsive shopping (CS) is a coping mechanism for people who are experiencing unpleasant emotions. This research looks into the darker side of consumer conduct, for example CS; it can help to develop a deeper knowledge of today's consumers and more effective marketing methods. In general, branded clothes are described as "apparel that a store owns, controls, and sells exclusively". In Pakistan some of branded apparel clothings includes Khaadi, Sana Safinaz, Levis, Limelight, Bareeza, Salitex, Beechtree, GulAhmed, Nishat linen, Cambridge, Cotton & cotton, Outfitters, Maria B, J. Sapphire, and so many. Between the variety of durable goods, branded clothes are most frequently purchased impulsively by buyers (Jamal, 2020).

It is found that compulsive purchasers frequently shop for fashionable clothing without recognizing that they have likely spent more than they can afford. In glimpses of previous research, this research intends add to the prior study by analyzing (CB) in young Pakistani consumers in the form of branded clothing's. According to Japutra et al. (2022), younger shoppers are susceptible than older consumers to compulsive buying. As a result, we present self-congruence materialism, hedonic value, and utilitarian value and hedonic happiness, hedonic fun measures for CB. Brand attachment (BA) is a term used to describe how people

feel about a product in the mean of branded apparel, is built as a mediator among the independent variables and (CB). The objective is to empirically investigate the problem for compulsive purchase (CP) among Pakistani young customers.

CP is derived from the concepts of BA and. As a result of the critical examination of recent literature on causes and factors of CBB and the issue requires factor from Pakistani perspective. However, in terms of CBB, little attention has been paid to brand- and store-related factors (Reema Frooghi 2020). in this particular study we want to know about branded clothing's with CBB.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Actual self- congruence leading to compulsive buying behavior

The term "true self" refers to what an individual is. The present self is somebody else that a person "is at the present time" (perceived reality), whereas the ideal self is what a person "would like to be." Humans naturally and subconsciously show empathy for a set of items and brands, meaning that the chosen brand shares some intrinsic characteristics with individuals (Kumar, 2013). Consumers may make purchases in order to realize their own ideas.

According to Desarbo and Edwards, consumers are more prone to engage in compulsive purchasing when they are experiencing high degrees of excitement and impatience. Because businesses aid customers in achieving their desired actual self-image, a greater fit between brand personality and actual self-concept fosters enthusiasm. As a result, clients may be more likely to engage in compulsive buying if they have a stronger self-congruence. Compulsive shoppers purchase items in order to boost their social image and meet their self-concept needs (Kukar-Kinney, Ridgway,&Monroe, 2012).

The above arguments led to postulation of following hypothesis.

H1. Actual self-congruence has appositive effect on CBB

In a similar vein, Hyun and Han (2015) discovered that customers are more inclined to develop a strong bond with companies that more accurately reflect their sense of self. According to research by Holenbeck and Kaikati (2012), consumers favor brands that appeal to their ideal and real selves. Similarly, Kaufmann et al. (2012) discovered that emotional brand attachment was positively influenced by the real and aspirational selves.

In terms of actual self-congruence, the predicated self-motive is the person's drive to act in ways that are consistent with its self-perception, also known as self-consistency motivation. Actual (SC) has significant influence on brand attachment because successful self-verification leads to trust, attachment, and positive feelings toward one's relationship partner (Burke&Stets,1999).

The above arguments led to postulation of following hypothesis;

H1a. Actual self-congruence has a positive influence on brand attachment.

The concept of self-congruence was recently used to develop a brand's emotional tie to its customers (Huber et al., 2018). Quick self-verification increases customers' attachment to their automotive brand (real self-congruence) Based on this findings, buyers' attachment to branded apparel clothing's may be influenced by self-congruence.

H1b. Brand attachment has a mediating role between ideal self-congruence and compulsive buying behavior.

2.2 Ideal self-congruence leading to compulsive buying behavior

Meanwhile ideal self-congruence is linked to image boost theory, which claims that people have desire to find ways to improve themselves.

Dittmar (2005) discovered that those who wish to change their existence are more likely to engage in compulsive purchasing. Personality goal motivates self-concept in terms of ideal self-congruence, leads to an individual's desire to improve oneself and maintain or increase positive self-esteem.

By expressing their ideal selves, compulsive shoppers purchase stuff in order to become their ideal selves, improve their social image, and raise their self-esteem (Kukar-Kinney, Ridgway, & Monroe, 2012; Jupatra, 2018). People who believe that material items help them achieve their ideal self-concept are more likely to engage in compulsive shopping.

H2. Ideal self-congruence has positive influence on CBB.

Self-congruence and brand attachment may have a positive relationship. According to Amjad, & Yousaf, strengthening self-congruence as a facilitator variable could boost brand attachment (2018). Customers who buy brands that are highly congruent with their ideal or genuine self, in other words, are more likely to develop an emotional relationship to the brand. The real and ideal selves have been used to predict brand attachment in the literature on consumer behavior (Liu et al., 2012; Roy & Rabanee, 2015; Usakli & Baloglu, 2011). For instance, Ekinici & Riley (2003) discovered a high correlation between brand attachment and customers' perceptions of the brand and their ideal selves.

H2a. Ideal self-congruence has positive influence on brand attachment.

According to prior research, (Brand attachment) appears to acts as a mediator among self-congruence (Japutra et al., 2018). Strong brand boosts purchase likelihood, resulting in obsessive shopping. This suggests that buyers who have a strong bonding to a trademark and that resembles their current or ideal self-concept are more likely to buy it.

Previous researcher has described that self-congruence has an indirect effect on customer behavior (Rabbanee, 2015). As a result, the current study claims that in the setting of branded clothing, (BA) mediates the relation between ideal self and compulsive shopping.

H2b Brand attachment mediates the relationship between ideal-self and CBB.

2.3 Materialism

"Materialism" refers to the tendency of financially motivated individuals to obsessively pursue

material possessions in an attempt to enhance their level of enjoyment (Belk, 1985, p. 4). A "set of strongly held views regarding the significance of possessions" is the definition of materialism (on page 308 of Richins & Dawson's 1992 book. Materialists frequently experience bad feelings, which they then try to cope with by purchasing their preferred brand of goods. As a result, materialists view buying positively (Arndt et al., 2004), particularly when it comes to items that they identify with and have strong emotional ties to (DelgadoBallester et al., 2017). Customers get pleasure from buying branded goods (Horváth & Adigüzel, 2018). Individuals make purchases to satiate their emotional attachment to a preferred object and their materialism (Richins, 2017). Customers' faith in their preferred brand is influenced by their dedication to self-identification and brand identity (Zhou et al., 2020). As a symptom of obsessive passion activity, belief shifts through materialistic purchases (Richins & Dawson, 1992). (Stenseng et al., 2011). Additionally, materialists frequently engage in obsessive purchasing (Faber & O'guinn, 1992; O'Guinn & Faber, 1989). Compulsive purchase behavior is also encouraged by the emotions and feeling of identity that consumers possess (Dittmar et al., 2007; Dittmar, 2005). As a result, materialism has been connected to privileged consumption and a high level of participation in trends The study's goal is to look into the link between materialism and compulsive shopping.

(Dittmar, 2004). When compared to others, "those who recognize superficial fundamentals have been noticed to have more economic worries and a greater willingness toward compulsive buying.

As a result, an increase in both expenditure and personal items connected to one another, indicating their higher social status. In today's customer culture, materialism is most important reason influencing Compulsive behavior. Materialism is also said to be used to influence people's purchasing decisions in order to increase their prestige and fulfil their wishes.

H3. Materialism has a significance influence on CBB.

Studies, tell materialistic customers' devotion to material items may serve as an alternate for their lack of social relationships (Zhengetal., 2020). According to prior research, materialism prefers brands and buying intent. The extent to which materialism fosters a strong brand connection for branded clothing usage, on the other hand, remains unknown.

H3a.Materialism has significance impact on brand attachment.

There is a clear correlation between materialism and compulsive shopping (Moschis, 2017).

Materialism has a significant impact on compulsive purchase behavior.

Materialism is a powerful indicator of compulsive shopping. As a result, it offers a framework for the concept of brand attachment as a mediator among materialism and CBB.

It lays the groundwork for the current study, which claims that in the setting of branded clothing, brand attachment brand attachment mediates the bond with Materialism and compulsive buying.

H3b. Brand attachment has a mediating influence on materialism and CBB.

2.4 Utilitarian value

Utilitarian value is a mission-driven action during the purchasing process; customers that adopt utilitarian ideals are typically task-oriented (Machleit and Eroglu, 2000). Previously mentioned "compulsive buying" can be described by utilitarian value, which review purchasing with a work mentality (Holbrook 1982). (UV), for example, may explain why people who perceive Christmas shopping to be a "women's work" go through what they consider to be a tough activity. Fischer and Arnold are good examples of this style of shopping (1990).

H4. Utilitarian value has significance influence on (CBB)

Furthermore, it is well acknowledged that there is a strong connection between shopping values and marketing benefits (Zheng, 2017). Brand attachment and purchasing behavior are assumed to be influenced by utilitarian value in particular. Tseng and Lee (2018) pointed out that affective, hedonic, and utilitarian incentives can have an impact on brand attachment.

"Cognitive" benefits brand attachment are utilitarian or functional gains made from brand experience.

H4a. Utilitarian value has a significance effect on brand attachment.

Brand attachment also mediate the association between compulsive buying behavior and shopping values among shoppers (utilitarian and hedonic) as a result of their will Customers who believe a significant amount of UV during purchasing are more incline to participate in (CBB) to gain more prestige from their purchase. As a result, brand attachment can help to bridge the gap between utilitarian value and compulsive purchasing.

It lays the groundwork for the current study, which claims that in the setting of branded clothing, brand attachment brand attachment mediates the bond with utilitarian value and compulsive purchase.

H4b. Brand attachment has a mediating impact on utilitarian value and compulsive buying.

2.5 Hedonic value

Hedonic values, on the other hand, are viewed as ones on action. Customers with hedonic values are more likely to seek pleasure or anticipation during the purchasing process and expect a joyful shopping experience (Zhengetal., 2020).

Shopping Centre managers, on the other hand, seek to make their shops more engaging and enjoyable for their patrons. The joyful and interesting buying experiences that may trigger hedonic values are most likely to affect compulsive purchasers, who buy items with an uncontrollable desire and do so frequently. Shopping hedonic values may influence future purchasing decisions. If they have a higher predisposition for compulsive buying, it is logical to presume that they have a higher proclivity for compulsive shopping.

H5. Hedonic value has a significance influence on compulsive buying

(HV), on the other hand, is considered to influence publicity and attachment (Jones et al., 2006). On the basis of such thoughts, the research finds that (HV) have a favorable bonding with brand attachment for branded objects. Benefits that are "emotional" may arise from a hedonic or sensory encounter with the brand (Voss et al., 2003, p. 317). The hedonic consumer value, as per Chauhan et al. (2021, p. 405), seems to be more specific and individualistic, as it is based on the hedonic consumption theory (Holbrook & Hirschman, 1982). Branded clothing has been classified as a high hedonic value product due to its expressive and sensory impacts (Rossiter et al., 1991).

H5a. Hedonic value has a significant impact on brand attachment.

According to Horvath (2018), hedonic shoppers have a strong desire to buy compulsively because they spend their money to satisfy their buying needs. Purchasers with stronger hedonic value are more easily enticed by sales promotions, which leads to compulsive buying, according to (Wang 2000). Similarly, observed connection between hedonic value and compulsive shopping. These findings imply that the stronger the bonding between hedonic value and compulsive purchasing is intermediated the deeper the brand attachment. However, how much does brand loyalty influence the link between utilitarian and (HV) and the compulsive buying of branded apparel clothing.

It lays groundwork for the current study, which claims that in the setting of branded clothing, brand attachment mediates the relation between hedonic value and compulsive buying.

H5b. Brand attachment has mediating effect on hedonic value and compulsive buying.

2.6 Hedonic happiness

People purchase to store rather than shop to acquire (Langrehr, 1991). Shopping is no higher level as a chore; rather, it has progressed into a groove and enjoyable activity (Jamunadevi et al., 2021). found that a shift in traditional cultural values toward marketing can encourage compulsive shopping. The hedonic shopping value varies by product category. It could be

linked to compulsive buying because it is more emotional in character than (UV) (Santini et al., 2019).

H6. Hedonic happiness has a significant influence on compulsive buying.

Additionally, it is recommended that high-status brands provide perceived pleasant value, which indicates hedonist motive, or conspicuously presented happy value. The primary aim of individuals is to make them happier. Brand attachment develops when fundamental qualities of self-satisfaction are met, such as satisfying and relaxing, as well as enriching and enhancing self-esteem. As a result, consumers consider brand personally significant. Creation of brand attachment will be positively influenced by product quality and perceived happiness. Consumer brand attachment is positively influenced by hedonism.

H6a. Hedonic happiness will positively influence brand attachment.

Swinyard and Smith (1983) when customer opinions were based on direct experiences, the results showed that purchase behavior could be predicted for the company. Customers develop brand attachment as a result of memorable experiences (Smith and Wheeler, 2002;). The stronger the bond between hedonic happiness and compulsive purchase is intermediated it will affect the relationship between hedonic happiness with branded apparel on CBB.

H6b. Brand attachment mediates the effect between hedonic happiness and compulsive buying

2.7 Hedonic fun

The objective of purchasing there is generally considered to be to meet ends, but there are also individuals who are looking for enjoyment or recreation. Hedonistic consumption encompasses features of behavior such as multisensory (the benefit of the whole function of the human senses), imaginative, and emotional consumption influenced by rewards such as pleasure in using aesthetic products and methods. The hedonic shopping value differs depending on the product category. It's possible that it's linked to compulsive shopping.

H7. Hedonic fun has a significance influence on compulsive buying.

Enjoyment influences the behavior of leisure travelers to some extent. The emotions connected with the phrases "fun," "entertainment," and leisure tourists (Duman and Mattila, 2005) emphasize "enjoyment". Besides that, it has been found that higher brand names focus on providing apparent ecstatic value, implying an egoist intent or noticeably displayed fun value. (Jamunadevi et al., 2021). The basic goal of consumers is to have more fun. Brand attachment develops when fundamental qualities of self-satisfaction are met, such as satisfying and relaxing, as well as enriching and enhancing self-esteem. As a result, people consider the brand to be personal and associated with them. The creation of brand attachment would be effected by customer satisfaction and perceived fun. Consumer brand attachment is positively influenced by hedonism.

H7a. Hedonic fun has positive influence brand attachment.

To get a competitive advantage in the market, companies aim to create memorable experiences. When customer opinions were based on direct experiences, the results showed that purchase behavior could be predicted for the company. Customers develop brand attachment as a result of memorable experiences (Smith and Wheeler, 2002 ;). The stronger the bond with hedonic fun and compulsive purchase is intermediated.

H7b.Brand attachment mediates the impact between hedonic fun and compulsive buying.

Compulsive buying and brand attachment

Brand attachment is concerned with the relation or reference between the brand and the consumer, Kleine et al (2009). define it as "the strength of the bond connecting the consumer with the brand," whereas Park et al. (2010) Buyers who have a stronger self-brand relationship are more

connected to the brand. Lee and Workman (2015) investigated the relationship among compulsive shopping and brand attachment. In quantitative research, they looked at the differences between high, medium, and low compulsive buying tendencies, as well as their stages of brand attachment. Remarkably, their result differs from those of Horváth and van Birgelen (2015). They conclude that consumers with more compulsive purchasing habits have stronger brand attachment. Compulsive purchase has been linked to emotional attachment to objects. This emotional effect improves customer's emotional bonds with brands, allowing them to feel attracted to brand (Dwivedi et al., 2019;). Previous has found that obsessive consumers (compulsive shoppers) have strong emotional attachment to the brands and are more likely to spend on goods.

In this scenario, stronger brand connection is possible to result in a higher inclination for (CB) of branded apparel. Given the concepts of brand attachment and compulsive buying, it's logical to assume that brand attachment is the driving force behind compulsive purchase. Individuals who have an emotional attachment to a brand are more likely to devote personal resources (money or time) to acquire it. Brand attachment nostalgia, according to Kessous, Roux, and Chandon (2015), increase the desire to acquire the brand. Consumers recollect about occasions when brand purchases brought them comfort.

Research framework

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework

3. Methodology

The study chose a quantitative methodology as the most appropriate strategy in order to analyze the relationship between independent variables and the dependent variable. Through the use of a survey methodology, the study offered an empirical snapshot of Pakistani consumers' attitudes and beliefs regarding branded clothing. Purposive sampling was employed in order to provide a targeted and representative sample for the study, given the focus on consumers of branded clothes.

In particular, the sample consisted of 361 respondents from graduate and undergraduate programs in Pakistan's twin cities, 187 of whom were female and 174 of whom were male. This strategy made it possible to gather data from people who frequently wear branded clothing in a targeted manner, guaranteeing that it was pertinent to the goals of the study.

The study sought to determine the precise correlations between the specified independent variables and the dependent variable of interest by evaluating the data collected through questionnaires. In addition to offering statistical precision, this methodological approach allowed for a better understanding of customer preferences and behaviors in the context of branded clothing in Pakistan.

4. DATA ANALYSIS AND FINDING

SPSS and Smart PLS 3 were used to analyze the data. SPSS was used to analyze the data and evaluate the demographics. PLS-SEM to test the measurement model, which was then followed by the structural model for this study, which included data reliability (via Composite Reliability, etc.) and validity (via Hetrotrait Monotrait/HTMT, etc.). R square and Q square were calculated to check the relationship between factors. The direct effect and mediation effect hypotheses were also tested using Smart P

Table I Demographics

	Respondents	Cumulative	%
Gender	Numbers		
Male	174	48.2	48.2
Female	187	51.8	100
Age (years)			
<18	12	3.3	3.3
18 to 23	123	34.2	37.7
23 to 28	107	29.6	67.0
28 to 33	68	18.8	85.9
33 to 40	51	14.1	100
Educational status			
Matric	6	1.7	1.7
Intermediate	36	10.0	11.6
Bachelors	123	34.1	45.7
Masters	116	32.1	77.8
MS/ MPhil	65	17.2	95.0

Measurement Model

4.1 VALIDITY AND RELIABILITY

The measure of composite reliability is used to assess the reliability of the construct, and it should be higher than 0.7 (Chin, 2010). Similarly, to verify the item's reliability, the measure of outer loadings must be determined and a score greater than 0.70 must be obtained. The convergent validity AVE scores should be more than 0.5.

Table II Reliability

<u>constructs</u>	<u>Items</u>	<u>loadings</u>	<u>CR</u>	<u>AVE</u>	<u>Hedonic</u>
Happiness	HP1	0.891	0.922	0.748	
	HP2	0.836			
	HP3	0.88			
	HP4	0.825			
Hedonic Fun	HF1	0.832	0.794	0.585	
	Hf2	0.71			
	HF3	0.705			
Actual Self Cong	AS1	0.627	0.775	0.464	
	AS2	0.696			
	AS3	0.744			
	AS5	0.651			
Ideal self cong	IDS1	0.777	0.785	0.493	
	IDS2	0.79			
	IDS3	0.777			
	IDS5	0.375			
Materialism	MAT1	0.818	0.838	0.483	
	MAT2	0.822			
	MAT3	0.843			
	MAT5	0.591			
	MAT7	0.294			
	MAT8	0.639			
Utilitarian Value	UV1	0.779	0.86	0.606	
	Uv2	0.819			
	UV3	0.77			
	UV4	0.774			
Hedonic Value	HV2	0.82	0.808	0.516	
	HV3	0.614			
	HV4	0.743			
	HV5	0.68			
compulsive Buying	CB1	0.467	0.733	0.414	
	CB2	0.631			
	CB3	0.731			
	<u>CB4</u>	<u>0.71</u>			

4.2 Discriminant validity with HTMT

Discriminant validity refers to degree of difference between the constructs, which can be evaluated using three criteria; 1) cross-loading of indicator, 2) Fornell and Larcker criterion and 3) Heterotrait-monotrait (HTMT) ratio of correlation. The values of this measure should be below 0.90, which means the variables are different from each other.

Table III Discriminate Validity

Table 4.3 Discriminate Validity

	actua I	brand	comp	Fun	happy	hedonic value	ideal	material	Utility
Actual	0.681								
Brand	0.69	0.623							
Comp	0.494	0.559	0.642						
Fun	0.45	0.379	0.399	0.753					
Happ	0.427	0.354	0.439	0.692	0.865				
hedonic value	0.442	0.364	0.408	0.731	0.764	0.719			
Ideal	0.459	0.374	0.287	0.477	0.489	0.431	0.70 8		
Material	0.448	0.396	0.434	0.31	0.296	0.124	0.45 2	0.692	
Utility	0.408	0.396	0.357	0.617	0.743	0.698	0.54 2	0.221	0.778

Table IV HTMT

Table

4.4

HTMT

	actual- self	Brand	comp	fun	happy	hedonic value	ideal- self	Material	utilit
actual self									
brand attachment	1.097								
compulsive buying	0.835	0.928							
hedonic Fun	0.722	0.614	0.673						
hedonic happiness	0.573	0.473	0.629	0.907					
hedonic value	0.678	0.56	0.661	1.099	0.96				
ideal self	0.732	0.59	0.509	0.758	0.64	0.875			
Materialism	0.63	0.53	0.62	0.535	0.325	0.576	0.822		
utilitarian value	0.584	0.544	0.539	0.883	0.909	0.955	0.79	0.349	

4.3 COLLINEARITY/ VARIANCE INFLATION FACTOR (VIF)

Once the construct validity and reliability are confirmed by measurement model assessment. Inner VIF is used to investigate the issue of collinearity.

VIF readings are significantly below the 3.33 criterion, as shown in Table 4.5.

(Diamantopoulos and Siguaw, 2006). As a result, we can conclude that this

model is not multicollinearity.

Table V Variance inflation factor

		<u>Table 4.5 VIF</u>	
		<u>brand attachment</u>	<u>comp</u>
Actual	1.602		2.299
brand attachment			1.98
Comp			
Fun	2.668		2.669
Happy	3.491		3.501
hedonic value	3.609		3.611
Ideal	1.789		1.79
Material	1.576		1.6
<u>Utility</u>		<u>2.736</u>	<u>2.779</u>

PLS-SEM MODEL

4.4 STRUCTURALMODEL: GOODNESS OF FIT &PREDICTIVE RELEVANCE

Finally, a blindfolding method is used to evaluate the model's predictive relevance (Hair et al., 2017). According to table 4.6, the dependent variables, compulsive buying (Q-square=0.161) and mediator brand attachment (Q-square=0.173) q-square values are above 0, which means that the model is predictive in nature.

Table VI GOODNESS OF FIT &PREDICTIVE RELEVANCE

	Table 4.6	Goodness of Fit & Predictive Relevance	
	R Square	Q ²	
Brand attachment	0.495	0.173	
Compulsive Buying	0.435	0.161	

4.5 HYPOTHESES TESTING

PLS-Algorithm was utilized to test the hypothesized relationships between variables using path coefficients. Bootstrapping was practiced for 500 samples. Table 4.7 shows the summary of relationships between variables. The results of H1 reveals that there is a significant influence of actual-self on compulsive buying i.e. actual-self (p=0). P-value are less than 0.05 as mentioned in the table 4.7, which supports the hypothesis. Ideal –self had the strongest influence on compulsive buying considering the f-square value of 0.016. The results of H2a) reveals that ideal-self has no influence on compulsive buying (p- value=0.0684). H3 reveals that materialism has positive influence on compulsive buying (p- value=.0.047). H4 utilitarian value has a positive significance influence on compulsive buying (p-value=0.091) H5 hedonic value has no positive influence on compulsive buying (p- value=0.665) H6 hedonic happiness has no positive influence on compulsive buying (p- value=0.988) H7 hedonic fun also has no positive influence on compulsive buying (p-value=0.223)

Table VII Hypothesis testing**Table 4.7 Hypothesis testing**

	B	SE	T Value	P Values	Decision	F Square
actual -> comp	0.332	0.039	8.518	0*	Supported	0.004
fun -> comp	0.01	0.046	0.223	0.823	not supported	0
happy-> comp	-0.041	0.042	0.988	0.323	not supported	0.017
hedonic value -> comp	0.02	0.047	0.434	0.665	not supported	0.013
ideal -> comp	-0.011	0.026	0.407	0.684	not supported	0.016
material -> comp	0.066	0.033	1.994	0.047*	supported	0.073
utilit -> comp	0.081	0.048	1.692	0.091**	supported	0.001

Significance level *0.05 **0.10

4.6. MEDIATION ANALYSIS

The mediation analysis is tested using the approach followed by Nitzl et al. (2016) by bootstrapping the indirect effect (Table 4.8). The results provide support that brand attachment mediates the relationship between materialism and compulsive buying (H3c: β 5 0.111, t 2.014). Similarly, brand attachment is also observed to mediate the relationship between utilitarian value compulsive buying (H4c: β 5 0.146, t 5 1.722). However, the results demonstrate that the mediating influence of brand attachment between actual self-congruence (H1c: β 5 0.593, t 5 11.743); ideal self-congruence (H2c: β 5 -0.016, t 5 0.319); Hedonic value (H5c: β 5 0.028, t 5 0.353), hedonic fun (H6c: β 5 0.022, t 5 0.273) and last but not the least hedonic happiness (H5c: β 5 -0.072, t 5 0.882)

toward compulsive buying is not supported.

Table VIII mediation Analysis

Table 4.8 Mediation Analysis					
	B	SE	T value	P Values	Decisions
fun -> brand attachment -> comp	0.008	0.029	0.261	0.397	not supported
material -> brand attachment -> comp	0.039	0.022	1.765	0.039*	supported
utilit -> brand attachment -> comp	0.051	0.034	1.476	0.07**	supported
actual -> brand attachment -> comp	0.206	0.046	4.482	0*	supported
happy -> brand attachment -> comp	-0.025	0.027	0.926	0.177	not supported
ideal -> brand attachment -> comp	-0.005	0.018	0.303	0.381	not supported
hedonic value -> brand attachment -> comp	0.01	0.028	0.341	0.367	not supported

Significance level *0.05 **0.10

5. DISCUSSIONS AND CONCLUSIONS

In a branded clothes scenario, the study's overall goal is to evaluate a research paradigm that defines the impact of young consumers' beliefs (self-congruence, materialism, and shopping ideals) on brand attachment and compulsive buying. As indicated in the following section, the findings are separated into three sections.

5.1 Implications and conclusion

This study expands findings to Asian nations like Pakistan, so extending the literature on compulsive buying behavior and making a substantial contribution to the ongoing discourse in Western countries like the United States (Harnish et al., 2017, 2018), Canada (Yi, 2012), and Europe. Has been classified as products

with high hedonic value. However, prior research has mostly focused on the benefits of brand attachment, such as encouraging brand loyalty (Japutra et al., 2014; Park et al., 2010). This study offers a fresh viewpoint by revealing the potential drawbacks of brand attachment, particularly its connection to compulsive buying behavior.

The study's findings theoretically add to the body of knowledge already available on consumer-brand relationships in a number of ways. First off, the findings of this study highlight a significant caution associated with consumers' identification with their preferred brands, despite the fact that previous research has generally supported this identification (Borghini et al., 2021; Hegner et al., 2017). A strong brand attachment may result in unfavorable consumer behaviors (Lucic et al., 2021; Aw et al., 2018). Therefore, the primary value of this study is to demonstrate the relationship between negative consumer actions and brand attachment.

Indeed, several academics have pointed out that businesses that support compulsive buying may encounter moral conundrums pertaining to their social obligations (Horvath & Birgelen, 2015) with a high hedonic value (Rossiter et al., 1991).

This research has practical consequences for marketers and practitioners, in addition to its theoretical contributions. It emphasizes how crucial it is to comprehend how brand attachment influences customer behavior, particularly in the case of younger consumers who are more likely to engage in compulsive buying. With a better understanding of these dynamics, marketers can adjust

their tactics to engage customers and make sure that product packaging and brand messaging have a good effect without unintentionally promoting obsessive behaviors.

In summary, this study provides actionable insights that can guide marketing strategies targeted at building positive consumer-brand interactions, in addition to furthering academic understanding by examining the complex relationship between brand attachment and compulsive buying.

5.2 LIMITATIONS AND FUTURE RESEARCH DIRECTIONS

While the current study provides valuable empirical insights and theoretical implications, several limitations necessitate further consideration. Firstly, the study's sample is confined to residents of Islamabad and Rawalpindi in Pakistan. Despite being populous and developed, these cities may not fully represent the diverse perspectives across Pakistan. A more robust approach would involve cross-cultural validation with a larger, geographically diverse sample encompassing various cities and regions within Pakistan. This approach would allow for a more comprehensive understanding of how different demographics and psychographic profiles perceive and engage with branded apparel (Lee and Workman, 2018; Ting et al., 2019).

Secondly, to enhance the explanatory power of the model, future research could expand the antecedents of brand attachment by incorporating additional relevant variables. Compulsive buying behaviors can be influenced by a myriad of factors

including personality traits, cultural norms, and socio-economic backgrounds. Integrating these variables into the study could provide a more nuanced understanding of the complexities underlying compulsive buying tendencies.

Lastly, given the rapid growth of online shopping platforms, it is imperative for future studies to explore compulsive buying behaviors within the context of online shopping environments. This would offer insights into how digital platforms and virtual interactions may exacerbate or mitigate compulsive buying tendencies in contemporary consumer settings.

In conclusion, addressing these limitations through broader sampling techniques, inclusion of diverse antecedents, and exploration of online contexts will not only strengthen the current findings but also advance our understanding of compulsive buying behavior across different cultural and technological landscapes. This holistic approach is essential for developing more effective strategies to manage and mitigate compulsive buying tendencies in today's dynamic consumer environment.

REFERENCES

1. Aaker, J.L. (1999), "The malleable self: the role of self-expression in persuasion", *Journal of Marketing Research*, Vol. 36 No. 1, pp. 45-57.
2. Akter, S., D'Ambra, J., and Ray, P. (2011), "An evaluation of PLS based complex models: the roles of power analysis, predictive relevance and GoF index", in *Proceedings of the 17th Americas Conference on Information Systems (AMCIS2011)*, Detroit, USA, pp. 1-7.
3. American Psychiatric Association (2013), *Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders (DSM-5®)*, 5th ed., American Psychiatric Pub, Washington, DC.

4. Aw, E.C.X., Cheah, J.H., Ng, S.I., and Sambasivan, M. (2018), “Breaking compulsive buying financial trouble chain of young Malaysian consumers”, *Young Consumers*, Vol. 19 No. 3, pp. 328-344.
5. Batra, R., and Ahtola, O.T. (1991), “Measuring the hedonic and utilitarian sources of consumer attitudes”, *Marketing Letters*, Vol. 2 No. 2, pp. 159-170.
6. Becker, J.M., Klein, K., and Wetzels, M. (2012), “Hierarchical latent variable models in PLS-SEM: guidelines for using reflective-formative type models”, *Long Range Planning*, Vol. 45 No. 5-6, pp. 359-394.
7. Banerjee, S. and Shaikh, A., (2022). Impact of brand nostalgia on intention to purchase brand extensions: moderating role of brand attachment. *Journal of Product & Brand Management*, 31(7), pp.1005-1017.
8. Bhatia, V. (2019), “Impact of fashion interest, materialism and internet addiction on e-compulsive buying behaviour of apparel”, *Journal of Global Fashion Marketing*, Vol. 10 No. 1, pp. 66-80.
9. Billieux, J., Rochat, L., Rebetz, M.M.L., and Van der Linden, M. (2008), “Are all facets of impulsivity related to self-reported compulsive buying behaviour?”, *Personality and Individual Differences*, Vol. 44 No. 6, pp. 1432-1442.
10. Bowlby, J. (1979), “On knowing what you are not supposed to know and feeling what you are not supposed to feel”, *The Canadian Journal of Psychiatry*, Vol. 24 No. 5, pp. 403-408.
11. Bridges, E., and Florsheim, R. (2008), “Hedonic and utilitarian shopping goals: the online experience”, *Journal of Business Research*, Vol. 61 No. 4, pp. 309-314.
12. Carpenter, J.M. (2008), “Consumer shopping value, satisfaction and loyalty in discount retailing”, *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, Vol. 15 No. 5, pp. 358-363.
13. Cham, T.H., Ng, C.K.Y., Lim, Y.M., and Cheng, B.L. (2018), “Factors influencing clothing interest and purchase intention: a study of Generation Y consumers in Malaysia”, *The International Review of Retail, Distribution and Consumer Research*, Vol. 28 No. 2, pp. 174-189.
14. Cheah, J.H., Memon, M.A., Chuah, F., Ting, H., and Ramayah, T. (2018), “Assessing reflective models in marketing research: a comparison between PLS and PLSc estimates”, *International Journal of Business and Society*, Vol. 19 No. 1, pp. 139-160.

15. Cheah, J.H., Ting, H., Ramayah, T., Memon, M.A., Cham, T.H., and Ciavolino, E. (2019), "A comparison of five reflective–formative estimation approaches: reconsideration and recommendations for tourism research", *Quality and Quantity*, Vol. 53 No. 3, pp. 1421-1458.
16. Chen, N., and Dwyer, L. (2018), "Residents' place satisfaction and place attachment on destination brand-building behaviours: conceptual and empirical differentiation", *Journal of Travel Research*, Vol. 57 No. 8, pp. 1026-1041.
17. Dittmar, H., Beattie, J., and Friese, S. (1996), "Objects, decision considerations and self-image in men's and women's impulse purchases", *Acta Psychologica*, Vol. 93 No. 1, pp. 187-206.
18. Duroy, D., Gorse, P., and Lejoyeux, M. (2014), "Characteristics of online compulsive buying in Parisian students", *Addictive Behaviours*, Vol. 39 No. 12, pp. 1827-1830.
19. Duroy, D., Sabbagh, O., Baudel, A., and Lejoyeux, M. (2018), "Compulsive buying in Paris psychology students: assessment of DSM-5 personality trait domains", *Psychiatry Research*, Vol. 267, pp. 182-186.
20. Eelen, J., Özturan, P., and Verlegh, P.W. (2017), "The differential impact of brand loyalty on traditional and online word of mouth: the moderating roles of self-brand connection and the desire to help the brand", *International Journal of Research in Marketing*, Vol. 34 No. 4, pp. 872-891.
21. Escalas, J.E., and Bettman, J.R. (2003), "You are what they eat: the influence of reference groups on consumers' connections to brands", *Journal of Consumer Psychology*, Vol. 13 No. 3, pp. 339-348.
22. Faber, R.J., and O'Guinn, T.C. (1988), "Compulsive consumption and credit abuse", *Journal of Consumer Policy*, Vol. 11 No. 1, pp. 97-109.
23. Le, M.T., 2021. Compulsive buying of brands, its antecedents, and the mediating role of brand love: insights from Vietnam. *Current Psychology*, 40(9), pp.4287-4298.
24. Dittmar, H. (2005). Compulsive buying- a growing concern? An examination of gender, age, and endorsement of materialistic values as predictors. *British Journal of Psychology*, 86, pp. 467-491

25. Fastoso, F., & Gonzalez-Jimenez, H. (2020). Materialism, cosmopolitanism, and emotional brand attachment: The roles of ideal self-congruence and perceived brand globalness. *Journal of Business Research*, 121, pp. 429-437.
26. Fitzell, P. (1982). *Private labels: Store brands and generic products*. AVI Publishing Company, Westport, CT. • Fornell, C., & Larcker, D. (1981). Evaluating structural equation models with unobservable variables and measurement error. *Journal of Marketing Research*, 18, pp. 39-50.
27. Gill-Simmen, L., Macinnis, D., Eisingerich, A., & Park, C. (2018). Brand-self connections and brand prominence as drivers of employee brand attachment. *AMS Review*, 8, pp. 128-146.
28. Gomez-Suarez, M., & Veloso, M. (2020). Brand experience and brand attachment as drivers of WOM in hospitality. *Spanish Journal of Marketing*, 24, pp. 231-246.
29. Gonzalez-Jimenez, H., Fastoso, F., & Fukukawa, K. (2019). How independence and interdependence moderate the self-congruity effect on brand attitude: A study of east and west. *Journal of Business Research*, 103, pp. 293-300.
30. Guthrie, M., Kim, H., & Jung, J. (2008). The effects of facial image and cosmetic usage on perceptions of brand personality. *Journal of Fashion Marketing and Management*, 12, pp. 164-181.
31. Hair, J., Hult, G., Ringle, C., & Sarstedt, M. (2016). *A Primer on Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM)*. Sage Publications. • Han, Y., Nunes, J., & Dreze, X. (2010). Signaling status with luxury goods: The role of brand prominence. *Journal of Marketing*, 74, pp. 15-30.
32. • Harnish, R., Bridges, K., & Karelitz, J. (2017). Compulsive buying: Prevalence, irrational beliefs and purchasing. *International Journal of Mental Health and Addiction*, 15, pp. 993-1007. • Harnish, R., Gump, J., Bridges, K., Slack, F., & Rottschaefer, K. (2018). Compulsive buying: The impact of attitudes toward body image, eating disorders, and physical appearance investment. *Psychological Reports*, 122, pp. 1632-1650.
33. Japutra, A., Ekinici, Y., & Simkin, L. (2014). Positive and negative behaviors resulting from brand attachment. *European Journal of Marketing*, 52, pp. 1185-1202.
34. Japutra, A., Ekinici, Y., Simkin, L., & Nguyen, B. (2018). The role of ideal-self congruence and brand attachment in consumers' negative behavior: Compulsive buying and external trash talking. *European Journal of Marketing*, 52, pp. 683-701.
35. Kim, R., & Chao, Y. (2019). Effects of brand experience, brand image and brand trust on brand building process: The case of Chinese millennial generation consumers. *Journal of International Studies*, 12, pp. 9-21.
36. Lim, X.J., Cheah, J.H., Cham, T.H., Ting, H. and Memon, M.A., (2020). Compulsive buying of branded apparel, its antecedents, and the mediating role of brand attachment. *Asia Pacific Journal of Marketing and Logistics*, 32(7), pp.1539-1563.

37. Lucic, A., Uzelac, M., & Previsic, A. (2021). The power of materialism among young adults: Exploring the effects of values on impulsiveness and responsible financial behavior. *Young Consumers*, 22, pp. 254-271.
38. Maccarrone-Eaglen, A., & Schofield, P. (2018). A cross-cultural and cross-gender analysis of compulsive buying behavior's core dimensions. *International Journal of Consumer Studies*, 42, pp. 173- 185.
39. O'Guinn, T., & Faber, R. (1989). Compulsive buying: A phenomenological exploration. *Journal of Consumer Research*, 16, pp. 147-157.
40. Pansari, A., & Kumar, V. (2017). Customer engagement: The construct, antecedents, and consequences. *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science*, 45, pp. 294-311.
41. R Development Core Team (2022). R: A Language and Environment for Statistical Computing. R Foundation for Statistical Computing, Vienna, Austria (<http://www.R-project.org>).
42. Rabbanee, F., Roy, R., & Spence, M. (2020). Factors affecting consumer engagement on online social networks: Self-congruity, brand attachment, and self-extension tendency. *European Journal of Marketing*, 54, pp. 1407-1431.
43. Zogaj, A., Mähner, P.M. and Tscheulin, D.K., (2024). The pursuit of the ideal self: An investigation of the relationship of authenticity and ideal self-congruence. *Journal of Consumer Behavior*.